

Parental knowledge and care-seeking practices towards pediatric ear infections: a study from Iraq

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ABSTRACT

An ear infection (EI) is one of the most common pediatric illnesses. This study aimed to assess parental knowledge, care-seeking practices, and factors associated with them. A cross-sectional study involved a sample of parents attending hospitals in three selected cities in Iraq. Data were collected with a questionnaire composed of three parts: i) Sociodemographic characteristics, ii) Questions related to knowledge of symptoms, risk factors, and complications of an EI, and iii) Questions related to care-seeking practices. The mean age of respondents was 34.99 (± 9.85) years. Females made up 58.90% of the sample. More than half reported holding tertiary education. Most participants showed satisfactory knowledge of EI symptoms (88.10%) and proper practices of seeking medical attention from a doctor or other medic (95.80%). Respondents with tertiary education had higher odds of having satisfactory knowledge (OR 4.63, 95% CI 1.18-18.19) and proper care-seeking practices (OR 14.96, 95% CI 1.12-28.80) than those with primary education and below. Current smokers had higher odds of having unsatisfactory knowledge (OR 0.12, 95% CI 0.02-0.70) than non-smokers. In conclusion, respondents had sufficient knowledge and care-seeking practices. Educational level was associated with adequate knowledge and care-seeking practices, and former smoking status was associated with unsatisfactory knowledge.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An ear infection (EI) is one of the most common health problems and a major cause of acquired hearing loss in pediatric patients [1]. By three years of age, about 80% of children would have developed at least one episode of an EI [2]. EIs are highly prevalent in children due to the anatomy of the middle ear [3]. An untreated EI carries a high risk of severe consequences. Hearing loss, as the most unfavorable outcome, impacts the quality of life of both children and their family members [4]–[7]. Existing literature has explored a spectrum of risk factors associated with an EI, ranging from child gender and atopic diseases to family smoking habits, living conditions and accessibility to health care [8]–[12]. Additionally, the outcomes of EIs are associated with parental knowledge about predisposing factors, healthy ear care practices, complications of ear infection, and care-seeking practices.

Previous studies revealed a relationship between poor knowledge and negative attitudes towards EIs, and a higher prevalence of these infections [13]. Low knowledge level among young parents was associated with the delayed care-seeking practices for patients suffering from chronic suppurative otitis media [14]. A recent study reported an association of parental care-seeking behavior with the socioeconomic status of the family and the perceived severity of the disease [15]. Parents with negative beliefs, perception of stigma and lack of knowledge were more likely to use home remedies rather than seek medical care for their children [16].

In Iraq, the literature on parental behavior towards pediatric EIs is scarce. As such, little known about parental knowledge and care seeking behavior which might affect the outcomes of pediatric ear infections. Thus, we undertook this study to assess the extent of knowledge and care-seeking practices among Iraqi parents of children with EIs. Results of this study may help healthcare professionals to address the gaps in preventing unfavorable EI outcomes and informs policies, design, and implementation of appropriate evidence-based interventions.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Study design

This was a cross-sectional study that involved parents of children aged between one and ten years who attended three selected teaching hospitals in three major cities in Iraq. Parents accompanying their children to the pediatric clinics of the teaching hospitals, whether for the first or subsequent follow-up visits, were selected randomly. Selected parents were briefed about the purpose of the study and ensured that participation is voluntary and no personal data, if any, would be disclosed to a third party.

2.2. Study tool

A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. The questionnaire was composed of three parts: i) Sociodemographic characteristics, ii) Knowledge about symptoms, predisposing factors, and complications of EI, iii) Preventive and care-seeking practices. The response options for knowledge questions were 'yes', 'no', and 'do not know', while the response options for questions on preventive and health-seeking practices were 'yes' and 'no'. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation.

2.3. Statistical analyses

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 24 software. Descriptive statistics were calculated and presented as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and mean (SD) for numerical variables. For the knowledge scale, the correct answers were given one point, while the incorrect and 'do not know' answers were given zero points. The answers to 14 questions related to EI symptoms, risk factors and complications were summed together to derive the knowledge score. Respondents who answered correctly to 50% and above of the questions were considered having satisfactory knowledge. The proper care-seeking practice was defined as a practice of seeking medical attention from a doctor or medical assistant (nurse). Logistic regression was used to determine factors associated with knowledge and care-seeking practices.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of respondents. Out of 278 distributed forms, 239 were completed, yielding a response rate of 83%. The mean age of the respondents was 34.99 (± 9.85) years. Females made up 58.90% of the sample. More than half (55.93%) were holding tertiary education, and less than 10% reported no formal education. The vast majority (95.30%) were living with a spouse. Over half (51.27%) were working, and about one-third (32.63%) were housewives. Most of the respondents were non-smokers (81.36%), had average income in comparison to their peers (75.85%), and owned a car (60.43%).

Table 2 shows the distribution of answers to the questions. The majority of respondents endorsed the following symptoms of EI: earache, rubbing ear, sleeping disturbances, fever, and ear discharge. In terms of the possible EI complications, hearing loss was the most frequently (72.27%) endorsed option, followed by learning difficulties (54.62%), speech problems (43.31%), and the spread of infection to the brain (29.24%). The respondents' ability to correctly identify the cardinal symptoms of EI, namely pain and discharge, might be attributed to their previous experience of managing childhood infections and their relatively high educational level. However, other studies found lower levels of knowledge about childhood EI [13]–[17]. Such discrepancy in findings might be due to the difference in settings, study populations and criteria to measure the level of knowledge in each study, as well as methodological strengths and limitations. Only a small proportion (8.37%) believed there were no complications of EI. Taking a shower or swimming, resulting in ear wetting, was the most frequently endorsed risk factor (88.28%), followed by scratching ears

with sharp objects (78.99%), using unsterilized examination set by the doctor (60.04%), cleaning ears with ear pads (62.18%) and cold weather (60.05%). Overall, 88.10% of participants showed satisfactory knowledge of ear infection symptoms. This finding is in tandem with some of the recent studies [18].

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

Characteristic		n	%
Dwelling	Mosul	108	45.57
	Falluja	65	27.43
	Baghdad-Hila	64	27.00
Gender	Male	97	41.10
	Female	139	58.90
Education	No formal education	23	9.75
	Primary	46	19.49
	Secondary	35	14.83
	Tertiary	132	55.93
Occupation	No working	25	10.59
	Working	121	51.27
	Housewife	77	32.63
	Student	13	5.51
Smoking status	Non-smoker	192	81.36
	Former smoker	11	4.66
	Current smoker	33	13.98
Income group	Below average	21	8.90
	Average	179	75.85
	Above average	36	15.25
Marital status	Living alone	11	4.70
	Living with a spouse	223	95.30
Car possession	No	93	39.57
	Yes	142	60.43
Age years mean (\pm SD)		34.99 (\pm 9.85)	
Number of children below 10 years mean (\pm SD)		1.63(\pm 1.01)	

Table 2. Parental knowledge of symptoms, risk factors and complications of EI in children

Symptoms	Endorsed with yes n (%)	Cause/ Risk factors	Endorsed with yes n (%)	Complications	Endorsed with yes n (%)
Earache*	215 (90.34)	Taking shower or swimming (water trapped in the ear) *	211 (88.28)	Hearing loss*	172 (72.27)
Rubbing ear*	209 (87.45)	Scratching ear with a sharp object*	188 (78.99)	Learning difficulties	130 (54.62)
Sleeping disturbance*	197 (82.43)	Using unsterilized examination set*	165 (69.04)	Speech problems	82 (34.31)
Fever*	168 (70.29)	Cleaning ear with pads	148 (62.18)	Spread to the brain*	69 (29.24)
Ear discharge*	145 (60.67)	Cold weather	144 (60.5)	Nothing	20 (8.37)
Hearing difficulty*	135 (56.72)	Ear wax*	123 (51.46)		
Running nose	67 (28.03)	Respiratory allergic disease*	111 (46.64)		
Cough	36 (15.13)	Family member with EI	97 (40.93)		
Vomiting	23 (9.66)	Smoking at home*	60 (25.53)		
Diarrhea	19 (7.95)	Vaccination	34 (14.29)		

*used in the calculation of knowledge score

Table 3 depicts responses related to preventive and care-seeking practices. Cleaning an ear with medical pads (73.22%) was the most frequently endorsed option for EI prevention, followed by preventing water from entering the ear (45.76%) and avoiding smoking at home (38.91%). The prevailing majority of participants reported that if their child had an EI, they would seek medical attention from the doctor (93.72%), and only a small proportion reported that they would seek help from any medic at the nearest clinic (7.53%). Overall, 95.80% showed proper care-seeking practices.

The high proportion of parents willing to seek proper medical care for their children might be attributed to the availability of healthcare services. Previous studies have documented the relationship between service availability and health-seeking behavior [19], [20]. Another possible explanation is that traditional medicine does not play a significant role in Iraqi society. Before the American occupation of Iraq in 2003, the national healthcare system witnessed spectacular advancement [21]. Fortunately, the healthcare system has retained its capacity to cope with population primary healthcare needs.

Table 3. Parental preventive and care-seeking practices

Prevention	Endorsed with yes n (%)	Care-seeking practice	Endorsed with yes n (%)
Clean ears with ear pads	175 (73.22)	Take the child to the doctor*	224 (93.72)
Prevent wetting of ear	108 (45.76)	Buy medicine and self-treat	47 (19.67)
Do not smoke at home	93 (38.91)	Take the child to the nearest medic*	18 (7.53)
Read about ear care	53 (22.18)	Do nothing, wait and see	9 (3.77)

*Used in the calculation of care-seeking practice score

Table 4. Factors associated with parental knowledge about EI in children

Knowledge		Crude		Adjusted	
		OR (95% CI)	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age	<30 years old	1		1	0.374
	30-40 years old	1.25 (0.42, 3.72)	0.686	0.79 (0.22, 2.81)	0.717
	>40 years old	0.65 (0.22, 1.87)	0.421	0.36 (0.08, 1.58)	0.174
Gender	Male	1		1	
	Female	1.19 (0.52, 2.7)	0.681	3.35 (0.59, 19.04)	0.173
Marital status	Living alone	1		1	
	Living with a spouse	2.65 (0.51, 13.89)	0.248	3.01 (0.5, 17.97)	0.228
Education	Primary and below	0 (0,0)	0.154	1	
	Secondary	2.39 (0.87, 6.61)	0.093	3.52 (0.91, 13.65)	0.069
	Tertiary	2.89 (0.88, 9.47)	0.079	4.63 (1.18, 18.19)	0.028
Occupation	Not working	1		1	
	Housewife	0.62 (0.16, 2.41)	0.493	0.14 (0.02, 1.08)	0.059
	Working	0.95 (0.25, 3.59)	0.935	1.54 (0.34, 7.05)	0.579
Number of children below 10 years		0.93(0.63, 1.38)		0.86 (0.55, 1.35)	0.518
Smoking status	Non-smoker	1		1	
	Former smoker	0.79 (0.25, 2.49)	0.683	0.7 (0.15, 3.21)	0.647
	Current smoker	0.31 (0.08, 1.27)	0.104	0.12 (0.02, 0.7)	0.019
Income group	Below average	1		1	
	Average	2 (0.61, 6.6)	0.255	2.83 (0.63, 12.66)	0.173
	Above average	1.65 (0.36, 7.47)	0.518	1.09 (0.15, 7.88)	0.935
Dwelling	Mosul	1		1	
	Falluja	0.94 (0.37, 2.42)	0.904	0.74 (0.21, 2.6)	0.634
	Hila	1.45 (0.49, 4.31)	0.499	1.88 (0.42, 8.39)	0.41

Table 5. Factors associated with parental care-seeking practices towards EIs in children

Care-seeking practice		Crude		Adjusted	
		OR (95% CI)	p value	OR (95% CI)	p value
Age	<30 years old	1		1	
	30-40 years old	0.46 (0.09, 2.28)	0.341	0.3 (0.05, 1.64)	0.164
	>40 years old	2.23 (0.2, 25.2)	0.517	1.05 (0.07, 15)	0.974
Gender	Male	1		1	
	Female	0.95 (0.26, 3.47)	0.942	2 (3, 4)	0.997
Marital status	Living alone	1		1	
	Living with a spouse	2 (3, 4)	0.999	8.19 (0.81, 82.75)	0.075
Education	Primary and below	1		1	
	Secondary	0.26 (0.03, 2.21)	0.217	3.39 (0.34, 33.4)	0.296
	Tertiary	1.91 (0.17, 21.72)	0.601	14.96 (1.12, 28.80)	0.041
Occupation	Not working	1		1	
	Housewife	0.32 (0.04, 2.76)	0.3	NA	0.997
	Working	1.06 (0.11, 10.53)	0.958	1.1 (0.1, 11.73)	0.939
Smoking	Non-smoker	1		1	
	Former smoker	0.38 (0.04, 3.38)	0.384	0.2 (0.01, 3.18)	0.253
	Current smoker	0.59 (0.12, 2.95)	0.518	0.85 (0.08, 8.98)	0.852
Income	Below average	1		1	
	Average	2.59 (0.5, 13.35)	0.256	1.88 (0.31, 11.25)	0.491
	Above average	3.68 (0.31, 43.32)	0.3	0.55 (0.02, 16.19)	0.729
Number of children below 10 years		0.79 (0.46, 1.35)	0.389	0.86 (0.44, 1.68)	0.667
Car possession	No	1		1	
	Yes	2.74 (0.65, 8.67)	0.189	1.33 (0.26, 6.91)	0.732

Respondents with tertiary education had higher odds of having satisfactory knowledge (OR 4.63, 95% CI 1.18-18.19) and proper care-seeking practices (OR 14.96, 95% CI 1.12-28.80) compared to those with primary education and below. Former smokers had lower odds of having satisfactory knowledge compared to non-smokers (OR 0.12, 95% CI 0.02-0.70) (Table 4 and 5). It has previously been found that female gender was associated with better knowledge about childhood EI [22]. At the same time, younger

people reported more frequent care-seeking practices [23]. Contradictory to published reports, gender and age were not associated with knowledge or care-seeking practices in this study.

Following the recent research findings, we expected that parents with low income would be less likely to seek proper health care [15], [18]. However, it was not evident in our results which might be attributed to the cost of healthcare in Iraq being affordable to the populations with different income status. So, the impact of income status on care-seeking behavior was not notable, which goes in line with other reports [13], [24]. Previous literature revealed that educational level was associated with both knowledge and care-seeking practices [18], [24]. Consistently, in our study, the respondents with higher education demonstrated better knowledge of the risk of EI complications and hence, were more likely to adopt proper care-seeking practices. Regarding the importance of education in improving health, maternal educational level was found to be associated with a range of health behaviors, including care-seeking practices and adequate child care [25]. World Health Organization advocates for improving women educational status, arguing that raising education rates for women would help to improve a wide range of health outcomes [26].

Although parental smoking has been reported to be a risk factor for childhood EI [27], as far as we know, no previous research has investigated the association between parental smoking and knowledge about EI in children. We found that former smokers had significantly lower levels of knowledge about childhood EI compared to those who had never smoked. Parental smoking might reflect their health ignorance. A few studies have shown a relationship between smoking status and a low-quality diet [28], [29]. Besides, limited health literacy was reported to be associated with being a smoker [30].

4. CONCLUSION

Respondents had satisfactory parental knowledge and care-seeking practices toward childhood EI. Educational level was associated with higher knowledge and care-seeking practices, and former smoking status was associated with lower knowledge.

Even though we have made the necessary steps to report generalizable results, some limitations were inevitable. The study included the hospitals in major cities; therefore, patients from rural areas might not have been well captured. Parents who are attending hospitals are likely to be more educated than those attending primary care clinics. Finally, we were not able to retrieve information about the frequency of EI among children, which might have provided some insight into the level of parental exposure to childhood EIs. Further study is suggested with larger area including rural areas.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Stevens, S. Flaxman, E. Brunskill, M. Mascarenhas, C. D. Mathers, and M. Finucane, "Global and regional hearing impairment prevalence: An analysis of 42 studies in 29 countries," *European Journal of Public Health*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 146–152, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckr176.
- [2] L. Monasta *et al.*, "Burden of disease caused by otitis media: systematic review and global estimates," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 7, no. 4, p. e36226, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0036226.
- [3] C. Paltura, T. S. Can, B. K. Yilmaz, M. E. Dinç, Ö. N. Develioğlu, and M. Külekçi, "Eustachian tube diameter: Is it associated with chronic otitis media development?," *American Journal of Otolaryngology - Head and Neck Medicine and Surgery*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 414–416, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.amjoto.2017.03.012.
- [4] S. Bakir *et al.*, "Mental health and quality of life in patients with chronic otitis media," *European Archives of Oto-Rhino-Laryngology*, vol. 270, no. 2, pp. 521–526, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s00405-012-2031-6.
- [5] C. N. M. Brouwer, A. R. Maillé, M. M. Rovers, D. E. Grobbee, E. A. M. Sanders, and A. G. M. Schilder, "Health-related quality of life in children with otitis media," *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 1031–1041, Aug. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.ijporl.2005.03.013.
- [6] M. A. Kenna, "Acquired Hearing Loss in Children," *Otolaryngologic Clinics of North America*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 933–953, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.otc.2015.07.011.
- [7] V. Yiengprugsawan and A. Hogan, "Ear infection and its associated risk factors, comorbidity, and health service use in Australian children," *International Journal of Pediatrics*, vol. 2013, pp. 1–7, 2013, doi: 10.1155/2013/963132.
- [8] F. Martines, D. Bentivegna, E. Maira, V. Sciacca, and E. Martines, "Risk factors for otitis media with effusion: case-control study in Sicilian schoolchildren," *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology*, vol. 75, no. 6, pp. 754–759, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ijporl.2011.01.031.
- [9] L. L. Jones, A. Hassanien, D. G. Cook, J. Britton, and J. Leonardi-Bee, "Parental smoking and the risk of middle ear disease in children: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Archives of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine*, vol. 166, no. 1, pp. 18–27, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1001/archpediatrics.2011.158.
- [10] J. Jervis-Bardy, L. Sanchez, and A. S. Carney, "Otitis media in indigenous Australian children: review of epidemiology and risk

- factors," *Journal of Laryngology and Otology*, vol. 128, no. SUPPL.S1, pp. S16–S27, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1017/S0022215113003083.
- [11] Y. Zhang, M. Xu, J. Zhang, L. Zeng, Y. Wang, and Q. Y. Zheng, "Risk factors for chronic and recurrent otitis media-A meta-analysis," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. e86397, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0086397.
- [12] S. B. Amutta *et al.*, "Sociodemographic characteristics and prevalence of self ear cleaning in sokoto metropolis," *International Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*, vol. 02, no. 06, pp. 276–279, 2013, doi: 10.4236/ijohns.2013.26057.
- [13] L. K. Qasim, Y. S. Bayunus, F. A. Alzubaidi, S. H. ALyami, and N. K. I. AlOsaimi, "Knowledge, attitude and practices towards otitis media in saudi arabia community," *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 2552–2556, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.12816/0042229.
- [14] J. P. D. Nshimirimana and K. B. Mukara, "Causes of delayed care seeking for chronic suppurative otitis media at a Rwandan Tertiary Hospital," *International Journal of Otolaryngology*, vol. 2018, pp. 1–5, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/5386217.
- [15] I. Villarreal *et al.*, "Healthcare-seeking behaviour of primary caregivers for acute otitis media in children aged 6 months to <30 months in Panama: Results of a cross-sectional survey," *BMC Pediatrics*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 3, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1186/s12887-016-0760-1.
- [16] N. F. Poole, M. K. Skilton, T. C. P. Martin, and M. C. F. Smith, "Knowledge, attitudes, beliefs and practices related to chronic suppurative otitis media and hearing impairment in Pokhara, Nepal," *Journal of Laryngology and Otology*, vol. 130, no. 1, pp. 56–65, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1017/S0022215115002996.
- [17] M. M. Alharbi, M. S. Almasri, A. Y. Aldayel, and S. M. Alkhonezan, "Parental knowledge, attitudes and practices towards paediatric ear infections in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia a quantitative study," *Sultan Qaboos University Medical Journal*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. e114–e121, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.18295/squmj.2019.19.02.006.
- [18] A. A. Adeyemo, "Knowledge of caregivers on the risk factors of otitis media," *Indian Journal of Otology*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 184–188, 2012, doi: 10.4103/0971-7749.104795.
- [19] L. Anselmi, M. Lagarde, and K. Hanson, "Health service availability and health seeking behaviour in resource poor settings: evidence from Mozambique," *Health Economics Review*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 26, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1186/s13561-015-0062-6.
- [20] A. Llop-Gironés *et al.*, "Inequalities in the access to and quality of healthcare in Mozambique: evidence from the household budget survey," *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 577–582, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1093/intqhc/mzy218.
- [21] S. Rawaf *et al.*, "Living conditions in Iraq: 10 years after the US-led invasion," *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, vol. 107, no. 5, pp. 187–193, May 2014, doi: 10.1177/0141076814530684.
- [22] F. Di Berardino, S. Forti, E. Iacona, G. P. Orlandi, U. Ambrosetti, and A. Cesarani, "Public awareness of ear and hearing management as measured using a specific questionnaire," *European Archives of Oto-Rhino-Laryngology*, vol. 270, no. 2, pp. 449–453, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s00405-012-1961-3.
- [23] A. M. Irwan, M. Kato, K. Kitaoka, T. Kido, Y. Taniguchi, and M. Shogenji, "Self-care practices and health-seeking behavior among older persons in a developing country: Theories-based research," *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 11–23, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijnss.2016.02.010.
- [24] K. B. Mukara, P. Waiswa, R. Lilford, and D. L. Tucci, "Knowledge and care seeking practices for ear infections among parents of under five children in Kigali, Rwanda: A cross-sectional study," *BMC Ear, Nose and Throat Disorders*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 7, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1186/s12901-017-0040-1.
- [25] B. S. Mensch, E. K. Chuang, A. J. Melnikas, and S. R. Psaki, "Evidence for causal links between education and maternal and child health: systematic review," *Tropical Medicine and International Health*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 504–522, May 2019, doi: 10.1111/tmi.13218.
- [26] S. Kuruvilla *et al.*, "The Global strategy for women's, children's and adolescents' health (2016-2030): a roadmap based on evidence and country experience," *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, vol. 94, no. 5, pp. 398–400, May 2016, doi: 10.2471/BLT.16.170431.
- [27] M. A. Moreno, F. Furtner, and F. P. Rivara, "Parental smoking and childhood ear infections: A dangerous combination," *Archives of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine*, vol. 166, no. 1, p. 104, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1001/archpedi.166.1.104.
- [28] A. Alkervi *et al.*, "Smoking status is inversely associated with overall diet quality: Findings from the ORISCAV-LUX study," *Clinical Nutrition*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 1275–1282, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.clnu.2016.08.013.
- [29] S. K. Raatz *et al.*, "Smokers report lower intake of key nutrients than nonsmokers, yet both fall short of meeting recommended intakes," *Nutrition Research*, vol. 45, pp. 30–37, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.nutres.2017.07.010.
- [30] C. Fawns-Ritchie, J. M. Starr, and I. J. Deary, "Health literacy, cognitive ability and smoking: a cross-sectional analysis of the english longitudinal study of ageing," *BMJ Open*, vol. 8, no. 10, p. e023929, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2018-023929.